

The Healing of Bartimaeus in Mark 10: 46-52: A Workable Model for Political Patronage and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The contemporary world emphasizes mutualism not just in the biological life of low classed organisms but also in higher organisms like human beings within the society. The mutualism as encapsulated here centres on such social variables as religion, economy, politics, morality and development which must work together to engender a better society for a happy living. In this study, it will be argued that religion is a springboard of whatever life can offer even in the contemporary world of globalization for development through the many areas such as the principles enshrined in the referenced text above. The work will adopt synchronic exegetical methodology, focusing on narrative criticism approach in eliciting data. The significance here will be to show that religion interplays with our daily activities and Nigeria can gain from it in her search for a true and useful political patronage and sustainable development. The research hope to make some findings to determine whether political patronage and sustainable development in Nigeria are achievable or hype in the light of the thoughts of Mark's Gospel 10: 46-52. The research will therefore make modest recommendations to encourage Nigerians in the best possible way that can facilitate the achievement of high political patronage and sustainable development through religious teachings and development.

Keywords: Critical Analysis, Political Patronage, Sustainable Development, Gospel

Introduction

A closer look at the theme of the 44th conference of the Nigerian Association for the study of Religions (NASR): Religion, Politics and Digital Economy in Nigeria points to two distinct facts which are Interactionism and Mutualism. These facts are very important in the lives of Nigerians. What can be garnered here is the need for all structures of the society to function fully through interactions and mutual understanding. These structures could be religion, politics, economy, technology, ethics, security, communication and so forth on the one hand; and human structures where we have the leaders and the led, haves and have nots and voters on the other. These societal human structures determine what should be and not be.

In this context therefore, religion stands out at the centre of interactions between human beings within any society. This is done mutually without let or hindrance in most cases. The mutuality here is the interdependence or interplay of religion with other societal structures or variables for a harmonious living. Understandably so, the text in question. Mark 10:46-52, is a religious factor that has so many principles that have direct bearing on the political behaviour of Nigerians that can make or mess the political patronage and sustainable development. More so is the fact that political patronage, if properly managed, is the key to political development that can engender good governance and the provision of the dividends of democracy to the people. This has input and output dimensions. The input and output in a decent climate lead to sustainable development. How this is achieved needs tact, concern, struggle and even repentance from old ways of life to new life devoid of selfishness, hatred, egoism, nepotism and the likes. One then asks, has Nigeria arrived at this point of cherished political patronage and sustainable development using these indices that come with interactionism and mutual interdependence?

Clarification of Concepts

Political Patronage: Political patronage cannot be easily discussed without a look at what politics is. Fundamental to this understanding is the fact that the word political is an adjective of politics describing that action that is found in politics; such as governmental, government, public, civic and so on. It is in this sense that this research adopts the coinage of politics by Okpaga Adagba as a set of human interactions concerned primarily with how decisions about resource allocations are made within a state.¹

Political patronage therefore comes as a result of political participation where the citizens of a particular state voluntarily involve in the political process or activities leading to the selection or election of some people to occupy leadership positions in a country (Attahiru, qtd. in Ahura and Tyoakaa).² It is through participation in political process that leads to political patronage as an expectation from the fall out of the political process. In this perspective, Rasak Bamidele opines that political patronage is the dispensation of favours or rewards such as public office, jobs, contracts, subsidies, prestige or other valued benefits by a patron (who controls their dispensation) to a client. The patron is usually an elected official or is otherwise empowered to make such grants. In return, the client supplies the patron with same valued services, such as voting for the patron's party or providing money or labour for electoral campaigning. The relationship between patron and client is typically unequal, selective and discretionary; the patron does not generally grant favours to all potential clients but picks and chooses among them.³ But sometimes, and in all cases, political patronage begins from the clients as in most cases the clients convince their later patrons to come and represent them in government thereby sacrificing their resources like money, goodwill, labour for them to be elected or selected. In this case, one can say that political patronage is a two-way traffic.

Sustainable Development: International Institute of Sustainable Development defines sustainable development as the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.⁴ Sustainable development becomes a foundation for today's leading global framework for international co-operation – the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This idea has been adopted by all United Nations member states in 2015, with 169 targets to reach by 2030 or sooner. That is the goal for a better society adopted by United Nation. But in Nigeria, can we achieve Sustainable Development through interplay of religion and political patronage?

The Problem of Political Patronage and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Nigeria as a geographical entity and a nation State has experimented a lot of Political Systems in a bid to achieve enduring democratic governance, Political Participation, Political Patronage to that can lead to sustainable development.

The Parliamentary system of government of the early sixties, to the presidential system of government, there appears that not much has changed. Political Patronage that is the key to Sustainable development has suffered a lot in the hands of leaders and the led alike. With this seeming scenarios, Achebe Chinua has lamented that the trouble with Nigeria is simply and squarely a failure of leadership. There is nothing wrong with Nigeria land, Climate, Water, air or anything else. The Nigeria problem is the unwillingness and inability of its leaders to rise to their responsibility, to the challenge of personal example which is the hallmark of true leadership if other countries are affected with natural disasters, Nigeria's own disaster is leadership failure.⁵ What happens is that the poor leadership of the Nigerian nation state has aggravated poor political patronage because our leaders are not sincere in their dealings with those the led who had placed them there. They exploit the gullible nature of Nigerians to cheat on them and deny them the dividends of democracy which has placed Nigeria's development to the lowest ebb.

The lack of sincere Political Patronage by the leaders (patrons) and the led (clients) has offered a fertile ground for conflicts and disagreements in the Nigerian Policy. Bearing this in mind, Okwori Helen avers that it has become a leading factor in the struggle for power and resource control.⁶ This is because, when a person or group feels cheated, excluded, victimized, neglected or marginalized, and for fear or shame of being stock at the last rung of the ladder, they antagonize other groups, which are normally the led and leaders themselves. These conflicts are mostly between the godfather and the godson. “Political godfatherism connotes the invasion of the political candidates by powerful sponsors, tending to complete possession for the purpose of selfish gratification (sic).”⁷

As a result, many see the godson as a political slave boy or political article for sale. It therefore cause friction as can be seen in what is going on in Rivers State of Nigeria today between Barrister Nyeson Ezenwo Wike, the immediate past governor of Rivers State and the current governor Sir Siminalayi Fubara. Wike is the godfather and Fubara is the godson. Their disagreement has reached a crescendo as the whole world watches. What happens therefore is that the masses of Rivers State will be at the receiving end in this power play. This affects good political patronage and sustainable development. Rasaki Bamidele et al say that regrettable in the face of dilapidation or non-sufficient existence of social infrastructure especially in states and local governments, public resources are used for political patronage⁸. In Nigeria’s Fourth republic, the emergence of “godfatherism” posed great threat not only to good governance but also to the socio-economic stability of democratic governance.

Political patronage which is also called patron-client politics is a worldwide phenomenon and not only peculiar to Nigeria. Elsewhere, the situation is not as bad as what is obtainable in our Nigeria. Osumah Oarhe feels that the dimension it assumes in Nigeria seems quite unique and uncommon and antithetical to democratic growth and survival. Democratic principles involve among other things free and fair election, constitutionalism, and the right of the majority to choose leaders and mandate them to make decisions and perform functions aimed at realizing the common good. The contemporary notions of patron-client politics negate such principles⁹. In Nigeria, this is not achievable as the principles are blatantly abused.

On another angle of the problem of political patronage is the heating up of the Nigerian polity through pervasive and increasing dysfunctional contemporary patron client politics and governance through the shows of brinkmanship. Osumah Oarhe emphasizes that various political weapons are deployed such as propaganda, thuggery, hooliganism, kidnapping, abduction, blackmail, threat and political murder against their clients when they renegade on agreement. A case in focus is the Adamawa 2023 governorship elections where gangsterism was employed by the resident electoral commissioner in Adamawa State, the Commissioner of Police to forcefully announce Aisha Binani as the winner, when in actual fact, governor Ahmadu Fintiri was the clear winner of the election.

More so is the consequence of negation of accountability, prudent management and the common good of the people which vital to democratic practice and governance. It is the pillar upon which privatization, ransacking and personalization of public funds and failure to utilize state resources to meet the genuine and legitimate needs of the people stands. The patrons encourage their clients to go ahead and loot the economy dry, believing that it is through this process that they would be paid back on what they invested in their clients during campaigns and elections. There is corruption, looting and sleaze in the management of the affairs of the state at the expense of the electorates.

In another dimension of the problem is the benefits gained when political patronage is at play. It goes a long way to affect sustainable development. What this entails is that appointments are skewed forwards certain persons as directed by the patron. Sometimes, the unqualified persons are appointed thereby fixing the round pegs in square pegs. What also happens is the execution of projects where other parts of the country are awarded more

projects and appointments than others claiming *it is our time*. In the light of the above Okwori Helen contends that it creates deep suspicion when it is perceived that one ethnic group (or part of a country) is dominating the political sphere of the country.¹⁰

Just as there is avalanche of failed political patronage it causes poor planning for sustainable development. The nexus here is enormous both in positive and negative terms. As can be observed, sustainable development comes mainly in three angles; economic, social and environmental. But due to the failure in achieving positive political patronage, sustainable development which is a direct beneficiary suffers. What happens, as explained by Kelly Bryan Ovie Ejumudo is that lack of good policy formulation, lack-hustle attitude of Nigerian government, in negating good political patronage has refused to embark on environmental care, encourages goes flaring and oil spillage and the Nigerian government attitude to sit on the fence without taking drastic measures on environmental protection for Sustainability shows that the required policies fall short of implementation and concern.¹¹

The section cannot be complete without mentioning insecurity, the impact of global economic recession and global pandemic (Covid-19), corruption, embezzlement and nepotism, youth restiveness, monolithic economy, failure of the past policies and non-continuity of government's good programmes are inimical to achieving good political patronage and sustainable development in Nigeria. Looking at the above, Azaiki (2007) contends that with regards to available infrastructure, Nigeria has been variously described as having one of the worst physical development indicators in the world. The country is at the bottom in human development factors, ranking 158 in the world in the 2005 Human Development Index.¹² This suits the description of Nigeria as the world's poverty headquarters by many people and outlets. All these are because of the poor political patronage that is hampering development and at worst sustainable development.

In the final analysis of the problem of political patronage and sustainable development, Ademola Julius Olajide quotes Ejimabo Nathaniel that most of the public office holders in Nigeria are people who have not shown the capacity for leadership but have manipulated the people and their ways into various leadership positions through corrupted electoral process. As such, Nigerian society has remained pauperized and the people are wallowing in abject poverty. Political leaders are supposed to harness and maximize the available resources of the country for greatest good of the people¹³. This is the crux of the matter within which there lies the problem of political patronage and sustainable development in Nigeria.

The Healing of Bartimaeus in Mark 10:46-52

It is noteworthy that human predicaments are everywhere and with individuals in one form or the other. It is the same with every society and every country. But there always rose personalities and situations that can help mitigate the yawning human gaps. Thorny issues such as nepotism, ethnicity, ill health, gangsterism, poverty, hooliganism, willful blockage and denial of opportunities are always the order of the day. These can cause uncertainties, neglect, quarrel and even war if not nipped in the bud. In this episode, Bartimaeus was the son of Timaeus. The name is a conjoined word from Aramaic; *bar* (son) and from Greek; *Timaeus* (honourable) meant for males.

Although, the name means honourable son, Bartimaeus the bearer of the name appeared to be unworthy, dishonorable because he was blind (Mark 10:46). This disability, in the eyes of the Jews, could be taken as his sins that led to his blindness since he was not born blind (Mark 10:51). He became a beggar, not by choice but circumstance, since it was common for the disabled among the Jews to be seen begging. But there seemed to be a bit of prejudice and discrimination amongst the Jews between the sick and those who were whole. The sick were despised as we can notice from the shout on Bartimaeus to keep quiet when he was shouting that Jesus

should come to his aid (Mark 10:47). Okwori Helen recognizes this phenomenon when she argued that when there is a relative balance in the social and economic status of people, there appear to be reduction in the level of prejudice and conflict among the people.¹⁴

Mark wrote this gospel to the Gentile Christians. Many might have heard that the Jewish Messiah to come could restore the Kingdom shackled by foreigners to Israel. But his coming does not reduce to worldly Kingdom but that of comforter of the afflicted, poor, low in social status and the needy. Therefore, rejuvenating the life of Bartimaeus through opening his eyes to see again was a wonder of the time and it added meaning to his salvific mission. That also gave hope to the hopeless of the Jews. Skinner Matt praises Bartimaeus “for knowing how to deal with people who tried to silence him before Jesus. His persistence adds substance to his bold expression of faith alone.... It is his unrelenting conviction that Jesus can and will rescue him from his need.”¹⁵ We cannot argue much with the above assertion because it is manifest in the action of Bartimaeus for his persistent shouting and throwing away his valued blind beggar’s coat with that conviction that he is no more returning to that ugly place by the road side. It could also be argued that Jesus saw his innermost faith and belief and sent those who obstructed and stopped him from coming to Jesus to work for him by bringing him to Jesus.

The story of blind Bartimaeus is a pointer to the fact that Jesus truly is the answer to human needs. He is the only one that can save people from their circumstances. He is a shining example for the mortal humans to copy by coming to the needy with helping hands and not jeering at them. Doing that can reduce social stigma and bring them to the course of happiness. In this connection, both the leaders and the led in Nigeria should uphold genuine service to humanity as their watch word. That desire for positive political patronage for a sustainable development should ginger every one up to give in their all for the development of Nigeria. This should be done as a duty, a call or vocation to help grow Nigerian state to enviable heights among the comity of nations where peace, unity, happiness and development would be enjoyed by all.

Implication of Mark 10:46-52 on Political Patronage and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

There are a lot of striking principles or lessons that can be learnt in this text that have implications or bearing on the Nigerian political patronage for sustainable development. A delineation is hereby made below.

1. There is a Country in Distress

The story of Bartimaeus is reminiscent with Nigeria. Bartimaeus was blind as seen in the scriptural text. He was disabled and handicapped for many years without solution. He felt the pains, despair, hopeless and isolated. He became a beggar against his wish. If we can relate this to political patronage in Nigeria, one could see that we the ordinary Nigerians always vote people into leadership positions to take care of our needs such as provision of basic amenities and general upliftment in terms of good support. We are handicapped because of the dearth of patronage to achieve sustainable development. Ikpilakaa Terungwa argues that physically challenged has succeeded in teaching us that life is glamorous when we move together, not when we look down or laugh at those who fall behind as if it is always their fault to be behind.¹⁶ It is not their fault to put one in a high position but their hope to get something better.

2. Belief in Support from the Patrons and Clients

What this principle teaches is that in all that we do, we should have the conviction to achieve our aspirations. This conviction stems from asking questions, getting knowledge of what is happening around us and having a go at it. It is the desire of every Nigerian to know what goes on in government from their representatives. When this is known, and from what we think of the people we have voted into power, we become convinced

that anything we ask, we shall get from them and we will also reciprocate their good gesture by re-electing them into power to sustain the development strategies they have envisaged. This conviction is only achievable when there is the capacity to represent citizens as well as provide policy choices that demonstrate their ability to govern for the public good. In that light, Adagba Okpaga argues that these capacities can be enhanced only through unchallenged freedom of equal access to those it's meant to serve; perhaps, these can be made possible through smooth relationships between all stakeholders.¹⁷ This then can convince all of political patronage and sustainable development.

3. **Demands made by Patrons and Clients**

In any human relationship, demands and concessions are made. These demands are the inputs made to the political class as done in democracies across the globe. These demands are processed at the decision making process (the leaders) and passed out as output which are the decisions taken. In this text, having known that Jesus was passing, Bartimaeus made a loud call on him to save his situation. He only made his point which serves as his demand or input. He was looking at what we can call today as dividends of democracy. What dividends of democracy means is the fact that it is driven by the majority who are more concerned with the ability as supporters to call on the leaders and point out to them their demands that we are patronized to enjoy these dividends. If we keep quiet, we will be forgotten. May be, Jesus would not have seen Bartimaeus, and he could not have been healed without his call. Our input matters a lot in getting political patronage to sustain equal development in Nigeria. Not just in the provision of amenities, appointments into key government offices by the leaders it means our persistent call on them to remind them of being neglected or forgotten. In this case, we can be patronized in Nigerian leadership space and can help in sustaining development to many areas.

4. **Political Gate Keepers or Fencers**

Bartimaeus was in want, despair, hopeless, a beggar against his wish and above all, he wanted to get solution to his predicament. In Nigeria, the general political space and the accruing benefits are in jeopardy. There appears to be no good plans for the citizenry. What we normally see is the haphazard arrangements made for the country where good political patronage and sustainable development suffers. Quoting John Maxwell, Ikpilakaa opines that "success is the privilege of contributing to the betterment of others".¹⁸ "Also, as the earth revolve around the sun, so should our lives also revolve around the son."¹⁹ Going by the above two references, one can aver that political patronage suffers like in the days of Jesus and with Bartimaeus' situation. Many people who were following Jesus prevented him from calling on Jesus for his need. Jesus did not even ask them to stop the man.

In Nigeria, once someone is elected or appointed into a high political office, you see a lot of people appropriating gatekeeping power to themselves so as to stop others from seeing the leader. This is done in many ways such as physical blockage of entrance to the doors of the appointee or the elected, telling lies against the constituents whom they despise, those very near to the leaders refuse to carry messages from constituents to them; as well as creating unnecessary enmity for the leaders by their lieutenants. These work against good political patronage and cannot help achieve sustainable development. But we can notice that development only succeeds where there is diffusion of ideas, information, acceptance and adoption or acceptance of a suggestion.²⁰ If these are hindered through acts of gatekeeping by those who are not even

appointed to do so, then the society suffers in terms of political patronage. When gatekeeping occurs, we should fight, shout and adopt other means to reach the leader so as to be heard.

5. Need for Altruism

Another area that is suffering neglect in the political sphere of Nigeria is the refusal of our leaders to hear the calls of their constituents. There is a lot of neglect. The leaders have no compassion on the led. They are not altruistic enough as compared to the tenet of altruism. Altruism teaches that we should be our brothers' keeper. Are our leaders keeping us the led in their hearts? This attitude agitates the minds of Nigerians who are well intentioned as well as the suffering masses. But God, as worshipped by our political leaders who professed Christianity, Islam and African Religions, all know Him to be the compassionate and altruistic God. They are all aware of the compassionate nature of the founders of their religions. Why then are they doing the opposite in Nigeria? This has prompted Asue Daniel to say that "the God we proclaim would be too harsh and people would say as they are seemingly saying... YOUR GOD IS MY DEVIL"²¹. And "Resultantly, that God becomes a devil to our neighbours, our fellow human beings"²². That is what Nigerians are saying to our leaders. In most cases they are jeered at and booed when they come during elections to solicit for support and votes. As a way of lamentation and also advice, Igboin Benson has asked political leaders to stop blaming their failures, lack of responsibility and accountability as an act of God. That, such actions and inactions of political leaders put God at risk of sharing in their blames.²³ These doubts endanger political patronage that cannot lead to sustainable development.

6. Needs Assessment from both ends

When Bartimaeus approached Jesus, even though it is always adjudged that Jesus can know the mind of anybody, he still had occasions he asked those who came to him for their wish. This was another of such occasions. What this teaches us is that, as political leaders, the followers too may have in mind what they need most especially where there are mirage of demands. You as a leader has to inquire to know what your followers want at a particular point in time. This is key to good political patronage and also development in the 21st century world, all countries under United Nations (UN) have ascribed to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). One striking point in this kind of development is knowing the wish of beneficiaries. When that is done, any project done to them makes them own it and put it to optimal use. The reverse is the case when their wish is not sought. The teaching of Jesus here calls to mind the requirements for our leaders to know their people and give them what they want and not what the leaders want. They can only do otherwise when they know the multiplier effect would be greater like the introduction of Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) phones to Nigeria.

7. Lack of effective Empowerment.

In answer to the question by Jesus what to be done to him, the blind beggar made a wise choice and asked for his eyes to be opened. "My teacher, let me see again". Although, he was blind and a roadside beggar, that habit could have become part of him and would have triggered him to request for more money. He chose to regain his sight which was an impressive choice made. His wish was granted and he regained his sight. In today's political life of Nigerians, that wish was a great one and could have been reserved for their children, wife, in-laws and cronies instead of the poor masses. It could have even been reserved for their tribesmen and women, and members of their faith. Jesus knew very well that Bartimaeus was not a Jew, therefore not his tribesman. But he went ahead and healed him. Kukah laments this nepotistic and religious bigotry when he

avers that ethnic politics is dangerous and beclouded Nigerians to the extent that political patronage was based on Fulani ethnic race and Hausa language was a tool to suppress other ethnic groups in the north as Hausa being an international language. Therefore, anything outside of these factors was deemed subjudice.²⁴

Today, people are after money instead of what they can do for themselves to facilitate being rich. They go into begging in the modern day Nigeria through dubious channels. Shishima laments the veracity at which begging has taken the centre stage in Nigeria through hook and crook. According to him, reasons are given as to scooping from the loot of Nigerian politicians who care less for the people and loot the nation dry for primitive accumulation of wealth. They cannot care for the needy. Another reason as he says is the non-empowerment of the people which led many youths and the aged to beg. Handouts are rather given out to people to perpetuate them in poverty²⁵. Jesus did not do that but empowered Bartimaeus to see again and be a man of himself with full abilities to seek for personal riches and not beg.

8. The Need for Positive Political Patronage for Sustainable Development.

It is pertinent to note that everybody wants care from people around them and government. When people face neglect from those they repose their trust in, the result is catastrophic. There is hatred, condemnation, harassment, abuse and rejection. The referenced blind man received his heart desire and was happy. Nigerians are visibly happy when they are cared for by their representatives. They receive accolades and names like Mr Infrastructure, Father Christmass, Our Son, Our Daughter etc. Come next election, such people are asked to go again and are voted into power. But those who do badly are rejected by the people come next elections.

In Benue State for example, this researcher notes that Senator Gabriel Suswam was massively accepted in his first four years as the governor for his good works in all spheres of life and was called Mr Infrastructure for the many infrastructural projects he executed. Okpaga also corroborates the above statement that Benue State enjoyed dividends of democracy across all sectors of the economy in an unprecedented manner because of commitment by Senator Suswam who was elected as governor in 2007²⁶. He had no problem during his re-election. Therefore, a good political patronage can be achieved when the two divides of rulers and the ruled are patronizing each other. This brings about development on a sustainable level.

9. Need to Accept our Shortcomings

Let it be known to every reader of this work that man is a dynamic being. He is subject to change depending on the prevailing situation. The blind Bartimaeus pulled off his cloak and threw away before finding his way to Jesus. Throwing away his cloak signifies many things: one, he might have been a careless and selfish person. Two, he might have engaged in many atrocities in his community or city. Three, he might have felt the cloak could entangle him as a blind man. Whatever is the case, there is this adage that “one who comes to equity comes with clean hands”. Therefore, he wanted to wash himself clean before coming to Jesus.

In political patronage for development, each and every one from the two divides of the leaders and the led should approach political participation with open minds. The openness with which Nigerians accommodate themselves will augur well for good political patronage which in turn ushers in sustainable development. Nigerians are not ready to pull off their coats and ready themselves for the art of good governance. In so doing, the dreams of our heroes past for a Nigeria of their dream is eluding us. Asue then captures the shattering experiences of Nigeria’s political landscape thus: “If we invoke history to be on our side one discovers that terrible things do happen in God’s name. Religion has been consistently used in manipulating people especially the poor helpless ones.”²⁷ This shows that we have not repented from our bad ways. As a result we blame God for all that we do negatively and for our failures without adjusting our old

bad ways – repentance. Igboin therefore cautions that “blaming God for human induced problems puts him at risk.”²⁸ Therefore, we are expected to do the right thing, at the right time, with the right intention, at the right place to achieve the right purpose.

The Challenge in adopting these Principles in Nigeria

There is plethora of challenges in the political life of Nigerians. These challenges hamper political patronage for a sustainable development, but few are discussed here. These are self-induced by the people themselves through ethnicity and religion which has a dividing thin line. Nigerians majorly belong to one form of religion or another and these are political actors that have made political patronage unbearable to most Nigerians. As a result, sustainable development is far-fetched. The ingredients oiling the illusion are ethnicity, shallow religion, spiritual blindness which Bartimaeus himself suffered, corruption of the highest order where there is primitive accumulation of wealth, injustice in all ramifications (judicial, economic profligacy, hatred etc.), bribery, thievery, and general negative manipulation of social, political, religious, economic and psychological order of Nigeria. But anywhere one goes, religious worship places abound like the Pauline Ephesus. It is Nigerians that will clear the negative coast of politics and imbibe the coast of determined sustainable development for us to be better. Igboin therefore argues that when bombs blast, when elections are rigged with stark evidence of human carnage, when whole villages are wiped out overnight, when corruption stinks and stings, when morgues are safer than the hospitals or the dividends of democracy are brutally denied the robbed voters, our politicians in chief are fast in referring to them as acts of God.²⁹ Another challenge appears to be negative begging. This has become a canker in the political life of Nigerians. It has gone to a stage that the leaders are molested, abused, insulted and called names by their clients when their personal, selfish and spurious demands are not met. These demands such as burial ceremonies, vehicles, clothes and even drinks are made. Others feel that it is their pensions which they must collect from the Patrons and Clients for earlier relationships. These acts are a bane to Political Patronage and Sustainable development. Sometimes, the people resort to telling lies to scoop from their benefactors.

In addition is the narcissist nature of Nigerian political actors who see nothing good done by others in the polity. This is the “Self” approach. Narcissism tends to make one excessively pre-occupied by oneself and is a growing sin of our times. Narcissism makes us blind to other people, to blindness and a denial of reality. We can all engage in narcissistic behaviours to a greater or lesser extent. This tendency is a clog in the wheel of sustainable development and positive political patronage.

The Way Forward

There are many challenges facing political patronage and sustainable development in Nigeria. But we as Nigerians need to stop blaming God for our actions and inactions, commissions and omissions. If we do so, Igboin asks: “Where are exactly the acts of men and women in Nigeria? What are the acts of Satan?”³⁰ The biblical chapter expounded in this work has shown us enough principles and directions we must face as enunciated above in this work. It is left to us to practice such principles with all our souls, body and knowledge to be able to arrive there at political patronage and sustainable development.

We should cherish democratic, social, economic and religious norms of our country and good norms from other countries for us to arrive there. We are also enjoined to abide by the 1999 constitution and create other good statutes for a better electoral process, good governance and the rule of law. Let us avoid acts that work at cross purposes with the expected result. Our leaders and the led should see that, rancor-free society and openness with the altruistic heart like Jesus can help mould a better Nigeria. Nigerians should also be proactive as the blind Bartimaeus.

Conclusion

This paper presupposes that in the contemporary world, there is interactionism and mutualism. There is nothing that successfully stands alone. That is why religion in whatever form cannot stand alone. It goes with other societal indices such as economy, agriculture, environment, politics, technology, communication, ethics, psychology, society and many more. These interactions, when mutually done, make a better living for a people such as Nigeria. Here, the paper was able to posit that religion works with politics to enhance sustainable development of individuals which has a multiplier effect on the economy. The example taken from the Bible point us to some principles necessary for Nigerians to imbibe for a better Nigeria of the dream of their forefathers and their present generations. In doing so, one has to tolerate one another as Jesus did in the quoted biblical text, knowing very well that Bartimaeus was a non-Jew but he saved him. We should accommodate other ethnic groups in our political calculations too. The Bartimaeus story, understood in this context challenges our narcissistic tendencies and offers instead the example of Jesus, the man for others. We should all be our brother's keeper.

Endnotes

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